

OPPORTUNITIES FOR INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20772425>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th June 2026

Accepted: 18th June 2026

Online: 20th June 2026

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, priority has been given worldwide to the introduction of innovative educational technologies into the management practices of leading higher education institutions. As a result, the efficiency of teaching and research activities in higher education institutions has increased, and the effectiveness of the expected social outcomes of higher education institutions in society has also improved. In particular, the use of innovative educational technologies in organizing educational processes in higher education institutions makes it possible to achieve the following results.

In recent years, priority has been given worldwide to the introduction of innovative educational technologies into the management practices of leading higher education institutions. As a result, the efficiency of teaching and research activities in higher education institutions has increased, and the effectiveness of the expected social outcomes of higher education institutions in society has also improved. In particular, the use of innovative educational technologies in organizing educational processes in higher education institutions makes it possible to achieve the following results:

- improving the efficiency of educational processes;
- ensuring the high competitiveness of highly educated personnel in the labor market in terms of their professional potential;
- strengthening the mobility of personnel with high professional competence;
- individualizing the provision of higher education services;
- expanding opportunities for the formation of a new higher education paradigm.

The essence of innovative management practice in the activities of higher education institutions is characterized by the fact that educational services are directed toward supporting individuals in their self-development as independent personalities based on their personal interests. Today, leading higher education institutions around the world that have

transitioned to innovative management practice are prioritizing the solution of the following tasks:

- introducing into practice the results of scientific research aimed at improving the structural organization of the educational process and teaching methods, including innovative teaching technologies;

- increasing the efficiency of independent learning processes organized in the education of students;

- developing the creative abilities of professors, teachers, and students, as well as creating sufficient conditions for this purpose;

- supporting students' cognitive activity;

- strengthening academic interaction between professors, teachers, and students.

According to the analysis, the fact that leading higher education institutions in the world have significantly advanced in terms of the development level of innovative management practice compared to local higher education institutions creates the need to study the possibilities of creatively applying their practices in the higher education system of our country on the basis of comparative analysis.

At this point, it is appropriate to pay attention to the essence of the economic category of "innovation." In economic literature, the definitions given by economists in explaining the content of innovation as an economic category can be divided into the following three groups:

1. explaining the content of innovation as an economic category in connection with novelty and know-how;

2. explaining the content of innovation as an entire process involving the production of a new product, including its technical and technological characteristics;

3. evaluating innovation as a driving force associated with the practical implementation of new ideas and thoughts, as well as the production of a new or improved product.

Taking the above into account, it can be concluded that innovation as an economic category is a broad concept. In particular, it has been identified that the introduction of innovations in the management of higher education institutions may take place in the following directions:

- research activities carried out in laboratories based at higher education institutions;

- increasing the efficiency of expected results from the provision of higher education services by improving technological processes and using existing resources;

- an approach aimed at fully forming deeply specialized professional knowledge, skills, and competencies in the development of an individual.

According to the analysis, the practice of innovative management in the activities of higher education institutions consists structurally of an interconnected competence-based approach, modern teaching methods, and infrastructure (see Table 1). This means that in higher education institutions with innovative management practices, priority is given to increasing the effectiveness of using interactive teaching methods based on modern information and communication technologies in the process of educating students, thereby training highly qualified personnel who meet the requirements of the labor market.

1-table.

Structural Composition of Innovative Management in Higher Education Institutions.

No.	Structural component	Essence
1.	Competence-based approach	The integration of the management practice of higher education institutions with the labor market. In this process, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for effectively meeting employers' demand for highly qualified personnel. To solve this task, it is necessary to use consumer-oriented marketing programs in the management process of higher education institutions.
2.	Integration of science and production	In managing the activities of higher education institutions, priority is given to developing the practice of commercializing the scientific research carried out by them. This is a characteristic feature of the entrepreneurial university model and creates appropriate conditions for strengthening the financial capabilities of higher education institutions.
3.	Modern teaching infrastructure	This refers to the wide application of products of the information technology industry in the organization and management processes of higher education institutions within the framework of the Industry 4.0 concept. Through this, along with developing the necessary infrastructure for the advancement of the "Digital University" concept, it becomes possible to diversify the types of higher education services provided.

The organization of the activities of leading higher education institutions around the world that have transitioned to innovative management practice is characterized by the development of special programs that take into account their innovative potential. In particular, higher education institutions such as the University of Massachusetts and the London Interdisciplinary School have developed the "Innovation Station" program for implementing innovative management; Chalmers University has developed the "Tracks" program; and the Moscow Technological Institute has developed management programs such as "The New Engineering Education Transformation" (NEET). Higher education institutions that have transitioned to management practice based on such programs are assessed by experts of international organizations as higher education institutions based on "Greenfield" management.

According to the analysis, the active use of innovative technologies in teaching processes at traditional higher education institutions has made it possible not only to increase the number of service types provided by universities but also to improve their quality indicators. In recent years, the priority given to reforms aimed at encouraging the use of modern information and communication technologies in organizing teaching processes in the higher

education system of our country may become a driving force for the transformation of management practices in higher education institutions. In this regard, it is necessary to develop national transformation programs based on the practices of leading foreign higher education institutions that have innovative management practices. We consider it appropriate to direct such programs toward innovative education.

List of references:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5847 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030”, dated October 8, 2019. <https://lex.uz/docs/4545884>
2. Narimanova O.V. The Concept of University 3.0: Prospects for Implementation in Russia under the Conditions of a New Technological Revolution // Personality in a Changing World: Health, Adaptation, Development: Online Scientific Journal. – 2019. Vol. 7. No. 2 (25). – pp. 650–362.
3. Vaseskaya N.O. Functions of the University in the Knowledge Economy // Business. Education. Law. – 2019. No. 2 (47). – pp. 86–89.
4. Shaping Teaching & Learning and Internationalization beyond the Pandemic. A qualitative research project following the IAU Report: Higher Education One Year into the COVID-19 Pandemic. International Association of Universities (IAU). France, 2023. 39 p.
5. COVID-19 and Higher Education: Today and Tomorrow. Impact Analysis, Policy Responses and Recommendations. UNESCO. April 9, 2020. 46 p.

